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Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of lung metastasis: FOXF1.

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Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the lung in breast cancer is difficult to treat and heterogeneous in nature, complicating its management (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in the lung metastases of humans with breast cancer. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the lung in humans with breast cancer, FOXF1, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of lung metastasis.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lungs to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lung metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: FOXF1.

Results

Figure 1: FOXF1 is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

- I. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2294	4.44E-02	1.056	-2.010306	-2.1234782	73.86	FOXF1	3917/22997	83.0

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of forkhead box F1, encoded by *FOXF1* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *FOXF1* changed more than 80% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of *FOXF1* messenger RNA in lung metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of *FOXF1* during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

Thus, we concluded that differential and increased expression of *FOXF1* likely defines the lung metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of *FOXF1*, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lung metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasize size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE56493 for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods. When data for GSE56493 is not present, it failed to satisfy validation, and was consulted but omitted.